

A New Monohedral Tiling by a Non-Convex Octagon

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Abstract

I present a new monohedral tiling of the Euclidean plane by a non-convex octagon. The shape is defined by explicit vertex coordinates, and a periodic tiling can be generated using translations and 180° rotations based on a simple edge-matching rule. This discovery contributes to the study of monohedral polygonal tilings and may inspire further exploration of non-convex polygonal tessellations.

1. Introduction

The classification of monohedral polygonal tilings has been studied for over a century [1,2]. Non-convex monohedral tilings remain an active area of research. In this paper, I describe a previously unreported non-convex octagon that can tile the plane monohedrally.

2. Shape Definition

The octagon is defined by the following vertex coordinates (in counterclockwise order):

$$\begin{aligned}v_0 &= (-0.80146, 0.06998) \\v_1 &= (-0.38515, 0.06998) \\v_2 &= (-0.16051, -0.20464) \\v_3 &= (0.2586, -0.20464) \\v_4 &= (0.40753, -0.5444) \\v_5 &= (0.40753, 0.44244) \\v_6 &= (-0.01041, 0.2558) \\v_7 &= (-0.38515, 0.2558)\end{aligned}$$

The concave vertices occur at v_1 , v_3 , and v_6 . A graphical representation of the octagon is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The non-convex octagon with labeled vertices.

3. Tiling Rule

The tiling can be generated by combining the octagon through translations and 180° rotations about the midpoints of selected edges. The primary edge-matching conditions are as follows:

- Edge v_1v_2 coincides with v_1v_2 of an adjacent tile.
- Edge v_0v_1 coincides with v_2v_3 of an adjacent tile.
- Edge v_2v_3 coincides with v_0v_1 of an adjacent tile.

A pairwise alignment of two tiles is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Two non-convex octagons arranged according to the edge-matching rule.

A periodic tiling of the plane obtained by this rule is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Periodic tiling pattern generated by the non-convex octagon.

4. Conclusion

This paper presented a new monohedral tiling by a non-convex octagon defined by explicit vertex coordinates. A periodic tiling was demonstrated using translations and half-turn rotations based on a simple edge-matching rule. Future work includes classification, searching for related tiles, and investigating the possibility of aperiodic variants.

References

- [1] K. Reinhardt, *Über die Zerlegung der Ebene in Polygone*, Dissertation, Universität Frankfurt, 1918.
- [2] M. Rao, “Exhaustive search of convex pentagons which tile the plane,” *arXiv:1708.00274*, 2017.